

High-level supercapacitive performance of chemically reduced graphene oxide

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Abstract: Commercial supercapacitors, mainly made of activated carbon, offers insufficient capacitance at high cost. Recently, graphene-based materials are emerging as smart alternatives. Reduction of graphene oxide (GO) is an elegant and important approach to produce reduced graphene oxide (rGO), because it holds the promise to closely resemble its physicochemical properties with pristine graphene. The conventional reducing agents such as sodium borohydride and hydrazine are strong reducing agents, and cannot be recycled. The fast reaction kinetics bring an imbalance in the desirable properties of rGO. Here, we present one-pot chemical reduction of GO in aqueous medium by an unconventional mild reducing agent (FeCl₂/HCl) where pure rGO is isolated and the reducing agent is recycled upon simple treatment of the filtrate with HCl. The fabricated all-solid-state supercapacitor of as-synthesized rGO exhibited significantly higher specific capacitance (171 F/g at 1.1 A/g), remarkable cycling stability (>80% retention of capacitance beyond 100,000 continued cycles), and flexibility (>500 bending cycles), which is comparatively better than those of rGO derived from conventional reducing agents. Use of commercially available organic electrolyte further boosted the supercapacitor performance (282 F/g at 1.8 A/g) of rGO.¹

Keywords: chemical reduction, reduced graphene oxide, all solid-state supercapacitor, durability

Reference

1. Plawan *et al.*, CHEM 2017, 3, 846–860.